

METHODOLOGY OF TEACHING ENGLISH

*D. Rafikjonov*¹

Abstract:

This article talks about the methodology of teaching English and the interactive methods used in its teaching.

Key words: Foreign language, communication language, pedagogy, technology, methodology, English language, CEFR, communication technologies.

doi: <https://doi.org/10.2024/sg72fs51>

Language learning is one of the most important areas in human society. Language, which is a means of communication, can be acquired practically in a natural environment, in the family, among the public or in an organized manner. Currently, many methods and ways of teaching English to the young generation, which is the demand of the times, from preschool and elementary grades, are being developed, and many researches are being conducted on the issues of practical application. The results of such research are sure to show their results.

As you know, English is currently the main language of communication in the world. Thus, the English language is evolving by constantly adding new words to its vocabulary. The influence of the English language on the Uzbek language is very large and it can be seen mainly in various fields of science, pedagogy, technology and social life. In many cases, we try to find the equivalent of the term from the English language based on the internal capabilities of the Uzbek language. But there are terms that are sold as international terms (or international words), which are used in the same form in English and Uzbek without any changes. For example, Greek and Latin words are widely used as technical and scientific terms.

"President's prize will be established for schools with high performance in foreign languages" - Shavkat Mirziyoyev. In fact, it is the task of us pedagogues to create school lessons and textbooks that can meet the standards of countries recognized by the world through the development of a foreign language. It is good that the students who can speak English are found in the first grade of the school. Especially, the number of students achieving international degrees in a foreign language is increasing day by day. Besides our national university, we are also pleased that more than seven out of one student is a student in the world's top 1000 universities. By the way, mastering science is a somewhat complicated process. Mastering a foreign language as well as one's own language depends on the skill of the pedagogue. The use of new pedagogical methods is also important and effective.

¹ *Rafikjonov Diyorbek Rakhim ugli, Master's student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages*

Compared to the traditional lesson, the student's mastery rate is higher in the lesson conducted using new technologies.

English language learning processes can be carried out in the following order:

1. Reading books and textbooks: Through reading books and textbooks, one can acquire useful knowledge to improve the skills of grammar, pronunciation, vocabulary, past tenses and previous studies.

2. Communication: In the process of learning English, there is a need to try to participate in the best reasons in the dimensions of the specific guides. You can improve your English skills through available programs, online and in person.

3. Online Platforms: In keeping with the lifestyles of pilots, several online platforms have tests, lessons and important information. For example, Duolingo, Babbel, Rosetta Stone, and other online classes can help you learn English.

4. Teacher support: With the help of teachers, a person can offer himself pleasant lessons, tasks and help in the process of learning English.

5. Practical training: For those who are interested, it is possible to try to improve speaking, writing, and writing skills through practical training. For example, serving in libraries and communicating with English or participating in theater productions.

These processes are the most popular ways to start learning, but it is important to recognize that each person's unique skills and lifestyles are the ways to participate.

In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the European Framework of Reference for Teaching Foreign Languages and Evaluating Knowledge and Skills of Foreign Language Teachers (CEFR). According to it, textbooks were created for students of general education schools and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, speaking, listening comprehension and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them. Educational technologies are effective use of modern information technologies in the educational process. It is also intended to increase the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process.

Currently, many methods and ways of teaching English to the young generation, which is the demand of the times, from preschool and elementary grades, are being developed, and many researches are being conducted on the issues of practical application. . The results of such research are sure to show their results. Teaching foreign languages to the young generation from their childhood has many advantages. One of the most important factors is that they love the language from childhood and arouse their interest in language learning. Because during the course of learning a foreign language, they get to know not only the language of that nation, but also the nationality, values and way of life of its inhabitants. Concepts and impressions about the world begin to appear in the student's mind. Knowing a language opens up many possibilities. It certainly has a positive effect on world travel, business, learning, and outlook. Foreign languages are taught step-by-step to schoolchildren, that is, elementary school students. In this process, the use of multimedia and oral teaching methods in a suitable way for the students of the 1st grade will have a good effect. English alphabet and writing skills are completely wrong for 1st graders without a full understanding and knowledge of their mother tongue.

Therefore, the first lessons of English are taught through games, multimedia tools and oral methods, and then when the students move to the 2nd grade, the literacy period is completely completed for them, and that's why. From the period, it is necessary to teach them the English alphabet and writing skills and to establish the formation of students' knowledge. In this way, they can form and develop a foreign language. The English language, with its many aspects and interesting features, attracts the interest of the student and leads to serious study of this language.

English language teaching processes are selected depending on the students' wishes and mastery. Most methodologies are tested by following processes:

1. The initial stage of learning: In the initial stages of language learning, the teacher is concerned with skills such as improving language skills, translating, learning the origin of words, learning to write words. conducts games and exercises.
2. Reading from the dictionary: Students use the dictionary to learn the words, phrases and vocabulary they need to improve their reading and writing.
3. Familiarization: The teacher teaches the students the temperature words, phrases and phrases in English. This methodology is poorly timed, but suitable for introducing the language into a modern context with a real meaning.
4. Reading and listening: It should be a fact that the next steps can support students to improve their listening through listening and listening process.
5. Writing: In order to acquire the ability to write the language, the teacher teaches the students to master the fluency in English, accounting for the scribbled texts.

In short, as a result of using innovative methods in English language classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to give quick and correct answers is formed. Such methods make students eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. This makes students active subjects of the educational process.

References:

- [1]. Abdullaeva Marhabo Rahmonkulovna. (2021). *Translation from English to Uzbek and its characteristics. International Journal of Innovation, Integration and Education*, 2 (2).
- [2]. Kh. Paluanova, M. Musumonova, K. Riskulova, Z. Qurbanniyozova. "List of pedagogical terms" 11/16/2012.
- [3]. Nasirova M.F. "Neologizm turlari va shakllanish omillari" *UzMU xabarlari*, 2024, 1-tom, 309-312 b.
- [4]. Passov Ye.I. *Kommunikativniy metod obucheniya inoyazichnomu govoreniyu. M.: Prosveshenie, 1991* 5. Xoshimov O'. Yoqubov I. *Ingliz tili O'qitish metodikasi. T., -2003*
- [5]. Yusupova S.A. *Translation of pedagogical terms into English and Uzbek languages, English and Uzbek terminology. 2021 year*
- [6]. Qizi, E. A. Z., & Qizi, A. S. B. (2023). *Pragmatics and semantics as special areas of linguistics. International Journal of Advance Scientific Research*, 3(11), 160-167.
- [7]. Erdanova, Z., & Eshdavlatova, A. (2024, April). *Lexical classification of language units. In Conference Proceedings: Fostering Your Research Spirit (pp. 43-47).*